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Investigation on Antioxidant Activity, Phytochemicals, and Cytotoxicity of the Peel from *Aloe Barbadensis* Cultivated in Vietnam

Author's Details:

Thanh Nguyen-Kim Le^{1*} Phuc Phan-Duc Pham¹, Truyen Duc Phung², Vy Thi-Ngoc Ha³

¹ Department of Applied Biochemistry, School of Biotechnology, International University, Vietnam National University-Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, 700 000.

² Department of Pharmaceutics and Physical Chemistry, Hong Bang International University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, 700 000.

³ Department of Biochemistry, School of Medicine, Keimyung University, Daegu, Republic of Korea, 42601.*
Corresponding author- email: lnkthanh1996@gmail.com

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Abstract:

This study investigated the phytochemical composition, antioxidant potential, and cytotoxicity of a 70% methanol extract derived from *Aloe barbadensis* peel. Phytochemical analysis revealed a significant presence of phenolic compounds (43.12 ± 0.19 mg GAE/g) and flavonoids (4.79 ± 0.21 mg QE/g). Antioxidant activity was assessed using DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging assays, yielding IC_{50} values of 153.02 ± 2.11 μ g/mL and 102.00 ± 4.18 μ g/mL, respectively, indicating competitive antioxidant potential compared to other *Aloe barbadensis* sources, despite being lower than some previously reported values. Cytotoxicity was evaluated on LO2 (normal human hepatic) and HaCaT (immortalized human keratinocyte) cell lines at a concentration of 1 mg/mL, demonstrating no discernible cytotoxic effects. These findings suggest that *Aloe barbadensis* peel represents a promising source of bioactive compounds with potential applications in various fields.

Keywords: *Aloe barbadensis*, antioxidant, cytotoxicity, peel, phytochemicals.

Introduction

Plants have historically played a pivotal role in human health, particularly within the medical field. Their diverse chemical constituents and perceived safety profile have facilitated their use in treating infectious diseases, spanning traditional herbal remedies to contemporary pharmaceuticals. Aloe vera, a plant renowned for its rich source of bioactive compounds, has been utilized therapeutically for centuries due to its purported curative and medicinal properties (Abdul Qadir, Shahzadi, Bashir, Munir, & Shahzad, 2017) According to the World Health Organization (WHO), *Aloe vera* is a succulent plant belonging to the Asphodelaceae family. Approximately 400 species have been identified and described, exhibiting a wide range of morphological variations, from 20 cm to 100 cm in height. Among these, four species are recognized for their significant biological activity: *Aloe barbadensis* (*A. barbadensis*), *Aloe perryi*, *Aloe ferox*, and *Aloe arborescens*. *A. barbadensis*, originating from Northern Africa, the Mediterranean region, and Asia, is particularly prominent.

Aloe vera is a cactus succulent plant formed by water storage tissues in the peels, growing to different sizes from 50-70 cm long in clusters under dry and hot climates. The green dagger-shaped peels that support it absorb

April 30, 2025

as much rain as possible. The structure of the Aloe vera leaf is composed of three layers (Femenia, Sánchez, Simal, & Rosselló, 1999): the peel, latex, and gel (40-45%) (**Fig. 1**) (Semerel, John, Dehaen, & Fardim, 2022) which is bitter yellow exudate and composed of abundant anthraquinone and aloin, and the innermost layer- a clear, soft, moist, colorless gel formed by the thin-walled tubular cells in the parenchyma (Patel, 2019).

Fig. 1. *Aloe barbadensis* Miller plant (left) - leaf (right). (A): leaf peel and (B): leaf latex and gel.

Aloe vera is commonly used as a material source in medicine, food, and the cosmetic industry thanks to its rich source of chemical substances containing more than 75 nutrients and 200 biologically active compounds, including vitamins, minerals, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, tannins, saponin, sterols, anthraquinones, and salicylic acid.

Aloe vera is now commercially cultivated worldwide, including Europe, Asia Pacific, Latin America, North America, and Africa, driven by its numerous benefits. Generally, the gel is usually separated from the peel to be forwarded to the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries, while the remaining peel also contains carcinogenic substances that are now considered waste and are not utilized (Guo & Mei, 2016). However, the demand for aloe vera gel-based products generates a significant amount of solid peel waste, estimated at 45% to 55% of the processed weight (Semerel et al., 2022). Industrial-scale gel extraction can produce over 4000 kg of waste monthly per facility, which, if improperly disposed of in the environment or used as fertilizer, contributes to serious pollution. This study aims to evaluate the biological potential of Aloe vera peel waste and develop new value-added products.

Materials and Methods

Sample harvesting and preparation

A. barbadensis was collected from Binh Thuan province, Vietnam ($10^{\circ}56'N$ $108^{\circ}6'E$) in January 2024. Mature and healthy leaves measuring 50- 70 cm in length and weighing an average of around 500 g were selected for the study. The whole peel was washed with tap water, and the gel was separated to collect the peel for drying in the oven at $60-70^{\circ}C$ for 24-36 hours. The dried peel were then ground to homogenize each sample into powder and stored in an air-tight zip.

April 30, 2025

10g of peel powder was extracted in methanol 70° as solvent with a ratio of 1:10 (w/v) for 3 days at room temperature then being refluxed in one hour in Soxhlet extractor. The crude extract was collected using a rotatory evaporator and stored at 25°C for later use (Kammoun et al., 2011).

Phytochemicals screening and analysis

The phytochemicals screening for tannins, oxalates, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and steroids were observed using varied colorimetric method (Ghosh et al., 2020), respectively.

Total phenolic content

Total phenolic content (TPC) was carried out using the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric (Sari, Ikawati, Danarti, & Hertiani, 2023). The TPC was expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/g extract. Shortly, 0.05 g of each sample was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol as a stock sample. In each well of the 96-well plate, 150 µL sample was mixed with 375 µL of Folin reagent followed by adding 375 µL of Sodium bicarbonate (Na₂CO₃). The blank was prepared with 150 µL methanol instead of the sample. The mixtures were incubated for 30 minutes before being measured at 765 nm using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The standard curve was calibrated using gallic acid serial concentration from 0 to 200 µg/mL.

Total flavonoid content

Total flavonoid content (TFC) was determined by the aluminum trichloride method (Sari et al., 2023). 100 µL of the sample taken from the stock was dissolved in 860 µL methanol in Eppendorf, and 20 µL of aluminum trichloride (AlCl₃) was added. The blank was prepared by replacing the sample with 100 µL methanol. The mixtures were incubated for 30 minutes, then 20 µL CH₃COOK was added, and 6 minutes later, the absorbances were measured at 420 nm by using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer. All experiments were tripled. The result was expressed by mg of quercetin equivalent per g extract. The standard curve was calibrated using quercetin at 0 to 100 µg/mL.

Antioxidant activity

2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical scavenging

The antioxidant activity of the plant extract was determined by 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay (Tabinda Nowsheen et al., 2023). A serial dilution of ascorbic acid from 0.78 to 12.5 µg/mL was used as the standard. The samples and standards were prepared with 500 µL of each mixed with 500 µL of DPPH solution (0.007% w/v) in an Eppendorf prior to be incubated for 45 minutes. The results were read at 517 nm using the UV-Vis microplate reader. Each of the measurements was triplicated. The percentage of inhibition was calculated by:

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs.blank} - \text{Abs.sample})}{\text{Abs.blank}} \times 100\%$$

Azino-bis(3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) radical-scavenging assay

The ABTS method with modification (Nesrine Benkhaira, Saad ibnsouda Koraichi, & Kawtar Fikri-Benbrahim, 2021) evaluates the antioxidant ability based on the ABTS^{•+} radical cation decolorization. The experiment started in a 96-well plate by mixing 10 µL of the diluted sample with 195 µL prepared ABTS radical solution, incubated in the dark for 30 minutes. The blank was prepared by DMSO instead of the extract sample. The absorbances were measured at 734 nm. The percentage of inhibition was calculated by:

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs.blank} - \text{Abs.sample})}{\text{Abs.blank}} \times 100\%$$

In vitro cytotoxicity assay

Cell viability was determined by the colorimetric MTT (Naskar, Dasgupta, & Acharya, 2023), (Javed & Shoaib, 2021) for the peel extract. The test was conducted using the human hepatic LO2 cell line (SCC064-

April 30, 2025

Sigma-Aldrich) and the immortalized human keratinocytes- HaCaT cells (T0020001- Thermo Fisher Scientific). The cell lines were maintained in 5% CO₂ at 37°C in DMEM supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and 0.1% antibiotics (penicillin and streptomycin).

The methanol extract sample was prepared by diluting in a medium solution at an initial concentration of 1 mg/mL and diluted in medium to reach the investigated concentrations of 500, 250, and 175 µg/mL. Firstly, 100 µL of the LO2 cells were seeded into 96-well plates (1.0×10⁴ cells per well) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, and the prepared samples were added. The negative control was the culture medium. The positive control was the reference drug. After 24 hours, the culture medium was discarded, and 20 µL of MTT reagent (0.5 mg/mL) was added. After 4 hours of incubation in the dark, the MTT layer was removed and all wells were carefully washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Finally, 150 µL of DMSO was added to dissolve the purple formazan crystals. The absorbances were spectrophotometrically measured at 570 nm.

Statistical analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate. The results were analyzed and expressed by using SPSS and Excel. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) method was applied to compare significant differences between solvents and samples ($\rho < 0.05$, $\rho < 0.001$).

Results and Discussion

Phytochemical screening

Table 1. Phytochemicals present in *Aloe barbadensis* peel extracted in methanol

Phytochemicals	Availability/Absence
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Steroids	+
Saponins	-
Oxalates	+
Tannins	+

Note: (+) present; (-) absent

In this study, the *Aloe vera* peel extracted in methanol was screened for preliminary phytochemicals and presented in **Table 1**. The extract revealed the content of six phytochemicals, including alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, and two anti-nutrients (oxalates and tannins). The alkaloid, flavonoid, and steroid presences contribute to the plant's biological properties as an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial agent. In contrast, the presence of two anti-nutrients may also show cytotoxic effects that need to be considered in consumption frequency and dosage (Sharma et al., 2020).

Total phenolic and total flavonoid content

Table 2. Total phenolic and flavonoid contents in *Aloe barbadensis* peel extract

	Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g)	Total flavonoid content (mg QE/g)
Standard curve	$y = 0.0047x + 0.0209$	$y = 0.0158x - 0.0258$
R ²	R ² = 0.9986	R ² = 0.9929
Quantity	43.12 ± 0.19	4.79 ± 0.21

Polyphenols and flavonoids are known to be anti-inflammatory and antioxidant compounds, helping to reduce the risk of inflammation and chronic conditions such as cardiovascular disease. The *A. barbadensis* peel extract

April 30, 2025

was prosperous in phenolic compounds such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, chromones, and anthrones. According to the reported data in **Table 2**, the peel extract claimed high phenolic content at 43.12 ± 0.19 mg GAE/g, which was approximately five times greater than the previous study in Sarajevo (Vidic, D., Tarić, E., Alagić, J., & Maksimović M., 2014) at 7.99 ± 0.26 mg GAE/g; and four times compared to a study in Serbia at 10.40 ± 0.28 mg GAE/g (Elferjane et al., 2023).

Moreover, *Aloe barbadensis* leaf extract in Vietnam (4.79 ± 0.21 mg QE/g) was also confirmed to be nearly two-fold higher than those TFC observed in samples studied in Serbia at 2.82 ± 0.2 mg QE/g (Elferjane et al., 2023) and nearly 1.5 times greater than the sample from Sarajevo (Vidic, D. et al., 2014).

Antioxidant activity

Table 3. DPPH and ABTS capacity of ascorbic acid and *Aloe barbadensis* methanol extract.

Assay	Sample	Calibration curve	R ²	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)
DPPH assay	Ascorbic acid	$y = 6.3529x + 0.197$	0.9921	7.84 ± 0.002
	Peel extract	$y = 0.2885x + 5.8054$	0.9834	153.02 ± 2.11
ABTS assay	Ascorbic acid	$y = 3.4378x + 0.0784$	0.9943	13.91 ± 0.55
	Peel extract	$y = 0.4818x + 0.4852$	0.9930	102.00 ± 4.18

Correlated with phenolic and flavonoid content as has been previously reported in the scientific literature review, the antioxidant activity was apparently recorded as moderate ability compared to that of ascorbic acid. The potential antioxidant activities of peel extracts were observed by DPPH and ABTS assay. The IC₅₀ value in the DPPH assay of the methanol extract was approximately 20 times higher than the standard ascorbic acid (7.84 ± 0.002 µg/mL), whereas, in the ABTS assay, the methanol extract's IC₅₀ value was nearly 8 times greater than the referent ascorbic acid ($102. \pm 4.18$ and 13.91 ± 0.55 µg/mL, respectively). Overall, both DPPH and ABTS assay results follow a similar pattern as TPC and TFC values, evidence that the higher the phenolic and flavonoid content, the more effective antioxidant activity (Rosli et al., 2016). A previous study reported significantly higher antioxidant activity in oven-dried, methanol-extracted Aloe vera skin samples, with DPPH IC₅₀ and ABTS IC₅₀ values of 1000 µg/mL and 400 µg/mL, respectively (Hossen et al., 2022) compared to the current study's findings of 153.02 ± 2.11 µg/mL and 102.00 ± 4.18 µg/mL.

In vitro cytotoxicity test

Fig. 2. The influence of *Aloe barbanesis* peel methanol extract on LO2 cell and HaCaT cell, $p < 0.001$

April 30, 2025

The observed lack of significant cytotoxicity of the methanol extract from *Aloe barbadensis* peel against LO2 (normal human hepatic cells) and HaCaT (human keratinocyte) cell lines, as evidenced by IC₅₀ values exceeding 4000 µg/mL and 3600 µg/mL, respectively, suggests a high degree of biocompatibility. These IC₅₀ values, derived from calibration curves with strong linear correlations ($R^2 = 0.97$ and 0.96), indicate that even at high concentrations, the extract did not induce substantial cell death. This finding is crucial for potential applications where cellular integrity is paramount, such as topical formulations or biomaterials.

The statistically significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in cell viability across the tested concentrations for both LO2 and HaCaT cell lines, while not indicating cytotoxic effects, suggest a possible modulation of cellular activity. This modulation could be attributed to the presence of abundant phenolic compounds, particularly tannins, which are known for their complex interactions with biological systems. While not cytotoxic, these compounds might be influencing cellular signaling pathways, proliferation rates, or other physiological processes. Further investigations are warranted to elucidate the precise mechanisms of this observed variability in viability.

The presence of high levels of phenolic compounds, including tannins, in the *A. barbadensis* peel extract is particularly noteworthy. These compounds have been extensively studied for their diverse biological activities, including anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and anticarcinogenic properties (A. Youness, Kamel, A. Elkasabgy, Shao, & A. Farag, 2021). However, in this context, the lack of cytotoxicity suggests that the observed phenolic compounds may exert their beneficial effects through mechanisms other than direct cell killing, such as antioxidant activity, modulation of inflammatory responses, or interference with specific signaling pathways.

Conclusions

The 70% methanol extract of *A. barbadensis* peel demonstrated a significant phytochemical profile, exhibiting substantial phenolic (43.12 ± 0.19 mg GAE/g) and flavonoid (4.79 ± 0.21 mg QE/g) content. Correspondingly, the extract displayed notable antioxidant activity, as quantified by DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging assays, yielding IC₅₀ values of 153.02 ± 2.11 µg/mL and 102.00 ± 4.18 µg/mL, respectively. While these values were comparatively lower than certain previously published data, they suggest competitive antioxidant potential to other sources of *A. barbadensis*. Critically, the extract exhibited no discernible cytotoxicity against LO2 (normal human hepatic) and HaCaT (immortalized human keratinocyte) cell lines at a concentration of 1 mg/mL, underscoring its potential safety profile to these cell lines. These findings warrant further comprehensive investigation into the detailed chemical composition and biological activities of *A. barbadensis* peel, with specific emphasis on its potential therapeutic applications in areas such as anti-inflammation and anti-aging. Moreover, exploring the utilization of this peel represents a valuable strategy for both elucidating its pharmacological potential and fostering environmental sustainability through the reduction of industrial waste..

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare to have no conflict of interest.

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April 30, 2025

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April 30, 2025

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